

**METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR USING WORLD INFORMATION
RESOURCES IN INFORMATION RESOURCE CENTERS OF EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS**

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Abstract: The article provides comments on the role and importance of information resource centers in educational institutions in increasing the spiritual and educational activity of young people, the effectiveness of using open and licensed world information resource bases published by the world's leading publishing houses, they contain comments on methods and technologies.

Keywords: activities of information resource centers in educational institutions, scientific and educational world information resources, EBSCO host information base, methods and technologies of using world information resources.

Today, the social changes taking place in the life of our country require a new approach to the activity of information-library institutions and the role of the young generation in society.

In accordance with the Resolutions of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "On the further improvement of information and library services to the residents of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated June 7, 2019 PQ-4354 In this context, the goals and objectives of the development of information-library activities must be consistent with the changes taking place in the country and international practice.

In this regard, to create a qualitatively new system of providing information and library services to the population, which ensures citizens' constitutional rights to free access to information, including national values and world culture, practical and fundamental knowledge, national cultural resources stored in libraries preservation and enrichment of the heritage, improvement of the organization of information and library institutions due to the wide introduction of information and communication technologies" [1].

This is a serious contribution to information-library activities, service to readers, replenishment and storage of funds, automation of library processes, scientific-research and

organizational-methodical activities, training, retraining and promotion of personnel, expansion of international cooperation.

The "information revolution" that began to take place at the end of the 20th century has a significant impact on the activities of libraries. As a result of this influence, libraries are increasingly becoming information-resource centers (in the following places, IRCs) equipped with modern information technologies.

Taking into account the requirements of the times, the importance of IRMs in educational institutions operating in order to meet the intellectual needs of the growing young generation, and at the same time to provide them with more comprehensive and systematic information, the role of remote education and his actions are incomparable.

Studying the resources organized by the information-resource center and its tools will help not only to increase the effectiveness of education, but also to develop personal characteristics of a person, which are necessary in modern society. Also, ARM is one of the leading structures that help in supporting the educational process, educational and methodological work and scientific research activities of educational institutions.

Today, ARMs of all educational institutions have a wide range of opportunities for users, and they have automation systems. These systems include cataloging, electronic catalog (EC), information-bibliographic service, bibliographic service using EC databases on optical discs or other libraries, user service (listing , giving, returning books, etc.), building a fund, including book exchange, registering periodicals and maintaining the corresponding EC, interlibrary subscription, automated preparation of bibliographic publications (including catalog cards), library includes functional departments such as management (enrollment, statistics, personnel, accounting, etc.).

At the same time, ARM users of the educational institution can regularly search for and use literature from the electronic catalog using the Internet. In particular, they use teaching manuals, textbooks, CDs, teaching-methodical sets, articles and other resources of professors and teachers of the educational institution.

In addition, educational institution ARMs should raise the provision of information-library services to users to a qualitatively new level, satisfy their scientific, educational, informational, cultural and business interests more quickly on the basis of modern information technologies and world scientific They are making a number of efforts to increase access to information resources.

In particular, open and licensed scientific and educational world information resources databases published by the world's leading publishers are widely used in educational institutions.

They are EBSCO host, ProQuest, Springer Nature, Web of Science, etc. These resources provide access to scientific articles, e-books and multimedia content for students, professors, teachers, masters, doctoral students (later users) and representatives of all fields. Also, the researches, important analytical data, best practices of developed countries, results of research (surveys, interviews, etc.), proposals and recommendations for system development are reflected in the most relevant areas of all fields.

So, how do the users of ARMs of educational institutions use such open and licensed databases of scientific and educational world information resources published by the world's leading publishers?

Below we will consider the possibilities of using the EBSCO host database. EBSCO hosts products and services for many types of libraries around the world. Its products include EBSCONET, a complete electronic resource management system and fee-based online research services with 375 full-text databases, a collection of over 600,000 e-books, subject indexes, and point-of-care directories.

To use the EBSCO host database, the user writes the information he needs directly into the search engine and uses the available information (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Access and search for information in the EBSCO host database.

Below, the user has the opportunity to get acquainted with the information found in the search engine and download it (Figure 2):

Figure 2. The process of uploading data from an EBSCO host database.

But today, effective use of databases of such global information resources is not fully implemented not only in educational institutions, but also in the use of scientific articles, research works and their analysis in the areas of industry. For example, the user is most often faced with language barriers, information literacy, ignorance of the search engine, etc.

Addressing these challenges requires a collaborative effort involving public institutions, educational organizations, libraries, and technology providers. Measures such as improving Internet infrastructure, promoting multilingual content, increasing information literacy programs, and conducting negotiations on convenient access to global information resources will eliminate these barriers and ensure full use of the knowledge resources of our country.

In addition, it is necessary to improve the methods and technologies for the effective use of world information resources by the users of ARMs of educational institutions. In order to effectively organize these noble works, any ARMs should have technical, software, information, linguistic, organizational-technological and personnel support.

Today, the introduction of the following methods and technologies for convenient use of world information resource bases also gives effective results:

1. Creation of digital libraries and online databases: Educational institutions should subscribe to digital libraries and online databases that provide access to a wide range of scientific publications, research journals, e-books and multimedia resources from around the world.

Advanced search functions and categorization tools like these help users efficiently manage and retrieve relevant information.

2. Establish an access control system: It is desirable to implement an access control system to ensure that authorized users, such as students, professors, and researchers, have secure access to subscription-based global information resources inside and outside the educational institution.

3. Implementation of open access initiatives: Information resource centers should promote open access initiatives that provide access to freely accessible scientific content, open educational resources, and thus expand the volume of open world information resources for the educational institution.

4. Establishment of interlibrary loan services: By using interlibrary loan systems, educational institutions can easily obtain resources from other libraries around the world, which allows users to access resources that are not available in their library's collection.

5. Implementation of digital archive and preservation system: Educational institutions use digital archival technologies to preserve and sort resources of historical and cultural importance, ensuring that valuable world information resources are accessible to future generations.

6. Collaboration tools and educational platforms: Information resource centers allow students and teachers to participate in group projects, discussions, and knowledge sharing activities based on the integration of collaboration tools and learning platforms that facilitate shared access to global information resources.

7. Implementation of multilingual search and translation tools: To accommodate different language preferences, information resource centers should include multilingual search capabilities and translation tools to help users search and access resources in languages other than their own.

8. Data analysis and visualization software: Institutions use data to process and interpret large data sets from global information resources, supporting research, statistical analysis, and evidence-based decision making.

9. Remote Access Technologies: As the demand for distance education and research increases, educational institutions must use virtual private network (VPN) technologies and secure remote access solutions that provide seamless and secure access to the world's information resources from off-campus locations.

10. User training and support systems: Information resource centers provide user training for students, faculty, and staff to effectively use the world's information resources, including search strategies, citation management, and academic knowledge.

Using these methods and technologies, ARMs in educational institutions can optimize the use of global information resources, enrich the educational and research experience of their academic community, while developing a global perspective and promoting academic excellence. The purpose of these methods and technologies is to inform users about open and licensed resources, how to use them, and to promote their search. Because global information resources enrich the educational experience by providing access to diverse knowledge, developing global awareness, and promoting intercultural understanding.

The use of such open and licensed scientific-educational world information resources in information-resource centers makes a great contribution not only to the educational institution, but also to the development of science. It also enables students and researchers to access and effectively use world information resources for scientific and research purposes.

To sum up, the importance of information resource centers organized in educational institutions is very important in increasing the spiritual-educational, social-political activity of young people. Also, it will be a wise way for young people to use the traditional and modern methods that have been experienced in the effective use of the world's leading databases.

It is natural that the creation of search systems based on new methods and technologies will serve as a suitable response point for the needs of young people. The most important thing is that if young people increase their intellectual potential by using such open and licensed scientific and educational world information resources bases in their scientific research work through ARMs in order to contribute to the development of our country, they will become highly moral and qualified personnel.

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